

Design of cooperative robotic arms with increased workspace for unknown extreme environments exploration

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Abstract: In constrained and unstructured environments, such as planetary surfaces or confined workspaces, traditional single-arm manipulators often face limitations in reachability, dexterity, and load balancing. To overcome these constraints, this work proposes a dual-arm robotic system with an integrated linear displacement mechanism, enabling coordinated manipulation, enhanced workspace flexibility, and adaptive task allocation across both arms. This article presents the kinematic modeling, workspace analysis, and static and dynamic analyses of a 5-degree-of-freedom (DOF) collaborative robotic arm system with integrated linear translation mechanisms, designed for rover-based manipulation and planetary exploration applications. The entire robotic system was developed both in a simulation environment and as a physical prototype. The kinematic analysis is based on the Denavit–Hartenberg (DH) methodology for the formulation of forward and inverse kinematics, while Jacobian matrix is also calculated to detect singularities and to convert cartesian into joint-space forces and torques. The workspace is determined by numerical methods and visualized, highlighting the advantages of the combined two arms with linear motions architecture. In addition, static analysis is performed to assess the mechanical stability under operational loads, as well as dynamic modeling to study the behavior of the system under time-varying forces and moments. The results confirm the suitability of the mechanism for handling demanding applications in extraterrestrial environments, combining high flexibility, large workspace and collaborative functionality.

Keywords: Dual Robotic Arms, Linear Displacement Manipulator, 5-DOF, Rover Cooperative Arms, Planetary Exploration Mechanisms

1 Introduction

The ability to explore and manipulate objects in unknown or unstructured environments is a critical and challenging problem in autonomous modern robotic systems, especially in applications such as planetary exploration, geological analysis, and rescue operations. In such scenarios, a combination of flexibility, precision, dexterity,

increased workspace, and operational reliability is required, which a dual robotic arm system designed to be adapted on a rover could successfully address.

Notable examples include the L3Harris dual-arm platform developed for defense applications [1], the Dexterity Mech system for industrial logistics automation [2], the GITAI Lunar Rover for extra-terrestrial surface manipulation equipped with a robotic manipulator that the end-effector can serve as a base, making it possible for the arm to change its base on top of the rover [3], and CERNbot, a dual-arm mobile robot for hazardous environment intervention at CERN [4]. In [5], the design and development of a dual robotic arm for industrial cargo transportation is presented, with emphasis on symmetrical arrangement and mechanical stability during the execution of transportation tasks. One robotic system for research in mobile manipulation is the PR2, [7], which combined a mobile platform, two collaborative arms, and advanced perception capabilities, serving as a reference for experimental reproducibility and application development within the ROS framework. The need for faster and automated cargo management in narrow and unstructured environments has led to the development of systems such as [8], a mobile robot with dual arms that efficiently performs truck unloading tasks through collaborative manipulation.

This work focuses on the design, analysis, simulation, and fabrication of a collaborative robotic system consisting of two 5-DOF robotic arms, each of which is integrated into a linear displacement mechanism. This combination aims to expand the functional workspace, improve collaborative interaction, advance dexterity and manipulability, and increase the adaptability of the system in complex environments. Recent developments have demonstrated the significant potential of mobile manipulators with dual-arm configurations in demanding and unstructured environments. The proposed approach enables each robotic arm to extend its effective reach across a significantly larger operational field. Furthermore, we address rover-specific accessibility limitations by allowing finer control over the reachability of distant or occluded targets. The system was developed entirely in a simulation environment and subsequently partially fabricated and validated as a functional prototype to prove its functionality.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the description of the system and Section 3 describes the kinematic analysis of the system and workspace, Section 4 consists of a static and dynamic analysis, Section 5 presents the simulation of the robotic arms while Section 6 presents the development of a prototype.

2 Description of System

The robotic system consists of a mobile six-wheeled rover [9] designed to operate on irregular and planetary-type terrain. Its construction is based on a lightweight, rigid frame that could support the placement of the robotic arms and the necessary electronics. The four independent wheel steering provides maneuverability and the ability to overcome small obstacles (as high as 150mm) as it is equipped with a Rocker – Bogie suspension, facilitating the platform's access to unstructured environments. Two articulated robotic arms with 5-DOF with a maximum reach of 675mm and

weighing 3,5 kgs each have been designed to be placed on the rover platform as shown in Fig. 1a. The manipulators are symmetrically distributed and connected to independent linear displacement mechanisms as shown in Fig. 1b. The ability to move the arms along the width of the rover enhances their range and allows for greater working space (Fig. 1c). Each arm could be equipped with an end-effector, which can be replaced according to the mission requirements (e.g., gripper, tool, sensor). The two arms can operate either autonomously or collaboratively. Collaborative operation is enhanced by linear mechanisms, which allow the relative position of the arms to be adjusted, optimizing the ability to perform tasks such as grasping, assisting one arm with the other, or passing objects.

Fig. 1. Sawppy Rover with the two linear robotic arms

3 Kinematic Analysis

3.1 Kinematics of the Rover

The mobile shown in Fig. 1 platform has six independent drive wheels connected with a passive rocker-bogie suspension mechanism to ensure continuous wheel contact with the ground, four of which (the two front and the two in the back) have an active steering mechanism, implementing a four-wheel steering (4WS) system.

Each robotic arm in the system is articulated, with 5-DOF, and consists of three revolute joints and two twisting joints connected in a serial configuration as shown in Fig. 1d where all the DH parameters are available, as well as the robot's dimensions.

3.1.1 Forward Kinematics

The approach is based on the DH method. The total transformation from the last joint on the end-effector to robot base is described by the product of the individual homogeneous transformations as in Eq. (1):

$${}^0T_5 = {}^0T_1 {}^1T_2 {}^2T_3 {}^3T_4 {}^4T_5 \quad (1)$$

where ${}^{i-1}T_i$ represents the individual transformation matrices between two consecutive coordinate frames i and $i-1$. Each of which is derived from the corresponding DH parameters as shown in Eq. (2):

$${}^{i-1}T_i = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_i & -s\theta_i & 0 & L_{i-1} \\ s\theta_i c\alpha_{i-1} & c\theta_i c\alpha_{i-1} & -s\alpha_{i-1} & -s\alpha_{i-1} d_i \\ s\theta_i s\alpha_{i-1} & c\theta_i s\alpha_{i-1} & c\alpha_{i-1} & c\alpha_{i-1} d_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where θ_i is the angle between x_{i-1} axis and x_i , d_i is the link offset, indicating the translation along the x_{i-1} axis, α_i is the links rotation, between z_i and z_{i-1} and L_i is the distance between z_i axis and z_{i-1} , while c is the \cos and s is \sin .

By substituting the specific parameter values, the final form of the table is obtained, which contains the $[x, y, z]$ position and orientation (as a 3×3 rotation matrix) of the end-effector in the Cartesian reference frame of the arm base. This analysis forms the basis for motion simulation, trajectory generation, and the design of position and force controllers for the mechanism.

3.1.2 Inverse Kinematics

The internal structure of the robotic arm, excluding the prismatic base displacement, follows a classical TRRRT configuration, consisting of five revolute joints arranged in a serial chain. This structure is representative of many industrial robotic manipulators and allows for conventional inverse kinematics techniques to be applied. The kinematic solution involves the computation of joint angles q_1 to q_5 that correspond to a desired end-effector pose, assuming a fixed base position along the linear axis as described in [10].

3.2 Complete Mechanisms Kinematics

This chapter focuses on the combined kinematic behavior of the two robotic arms mounted on a common mobile platform. Each arm has its own local coordinate system, with reference to which the kinematic analysis is performed. The overall kinematic model of an arm includes both the linear displacement of the base and the sequence of rotary joints. The position and orientation of the end-effector are obtained through the combined global homogeneous transformation function shown in Eq. (4) and (5):

$$T_{global} = T_{linear} * T_{arm}(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_5) \quad (4)$$

$$T_{linear}(d_L) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & d_L \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where T_{linear} refers to the transformation due to the linear movement of the base along the x -axis, while T_{arm} describes the internal transformation of the arm for given joint angles q_i . The selection of the appropriate arm for accessing a point in space is based on geometric and kinematic criteria. Initially, it is evaluated whether the desired point P_{target}^i is located within the workspace of each arm with the use of Eq. (6).

$$P_{target}^i \in W^{(i)} \quad (6)$$

where $W^{(i)}$ is the workspace and P_{target}^i is the desired point.

Then, the inverse kinematics is calculated for each one and, if valid solutions are obtained through Eq. (7),

$$q_i = IK(P_{local}^i) \quad (7)$$

the arm that ensures the lowest kinematic load or offers the most favorable access geometry is selected. For the effective cooperation of the two arms, it is necessary to develop a selection procedure, through which it is determined which arm will be mobilized to execute a command towards a specific point in space. After verifying the possibility of executing the command by each arm, a Euclidean cost criterion measuring the required joint displacement from the current configuration is calculated in Eq. (8) and the one that offers the lowest cost is selected.

$$C^i = \|q^{(i)} - q_{current}^{(i)}\|_2 \quad (8)$$

This procedure is summarized in the following block diagram Fig. 3:

Fig. 2. Block Diagram of Arm Selection Procedure

When both robotic arms operate, within the share workspace their motion and position is monitored. A complete model of the dual arm system is employed to evaluate possible collision between the bodies of the manipulators as well as the end-effectors. This ensures that neither the end-effectors nor any link of one manipulator comes into contact with the other arm or the rover. The conflicts are detected through trajectory analysis and collision constraints. In the event of detection a possible collision the trajectory of one arm is adjusted accordingly.

3.3 Workspace

The simultaneous operation of both manipulators in the same environment makes it necessary to study the total collaborative workspace. The workspace analysis was performed using kinematic sampling in two planes (YX in Fig. 3a and ZY in Fig. 3b), while the full three-dimensional workspace is obtained as the union of the points that can be reached by at least one of the two arms. The results highlight three main areas:

- Individual Workspace: Areas where only one of the two arms can move shown in Fig. 3 shown with blue paint for the left manipulator and with red color for the right manipulator.
- Collaborative Workspace: Areas that are within the reach of both arms and allow simultaneous or coordinated work (e.g., receiving and delivering items) shown in Fig.3 highlighted with green color.
- Extension via base: The ability to shift the base allows for changing workspace boundaries and increasing the shared area shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Workspace where the 2 arms can work collaboratively

The integration of a linear displacement mechanism along on each robotic manipulator results in a 16% increase of the reachable workspace on YX plane. Integrating the mechanism on both manipulators yields an increase of 32%.

4 Analysis of the Mechanism

4.1 Static Analysis

To evaluate the joint loads under self-weight and external forces, the geometric Jacobian matrix $JER^{6 \times 5}$ of the manipulator was derived based on its forward kinematic model. Each joint was modeled as revolute, and the Jacobian was computed using the standard geometric formulation. The Jacobian was evaluated numerically for the worst-

case configuration, in which the arm is fully extended: $\theta_1=0^\circ$, $\theta_2=90^\circ$, $\theta_3=0^\circ$, $\theta_4=0^\circ$, $\theta_5=0^\circ$. The linear displacement along the base x-axis was not included in the Jacobian-based torque analysis, as it does not affect the relative geometry or internal torque distribution of the revolute joints. Its influence is limited to translating the entire manipulator in space, without contributing to joint loads under vertical external forces.

To simulate a loading scenario, a vertical downward force of 1kg in earth's gravity was applied at the end-effector. In parallel, the gravitational torques from the arm's own mass were considered. The total moving mass of the arm was estimated at 1.5kg, distributed across the last three links. Gravitational torques were computed for each joint by summing the torques due to all distal links and their respective moment arms. The total joint torque vector was computed by Eq. (9):

$$\tau = J^T \times F_{ext} + \vec{\tau}_{gravity} \quad (9)$$

The resulting torques (in N·m) for this worst-case pose are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Joint torques for specified orientation

Joint	1	2	3	4	5
Total Torque(N·m)	0.0	-6.44	-4.24	-2.27	0.0

These calculations were used to guide the motor selection for the actuation of the robotic arm. By applying a safety factor of $n=1.5$ the maximum required joint torque was determined to be approximately 9.66 N·m. To meet this requirement, two ST3215 [11] servo motors, each rated at 3 N·m peak torque, were selected for Joint 2, coupled through a 3:1 gear reduction. This configuration provides a total theoretical available output torque of 18 N·m, sufficiently exceeding the design requirement. The same servo motors were used for every joint with a gear reduction of 4:1 for joint 1, 2:1 for joint 3, 1,5:1 for joint 4 and 1:1 for joint 5.

4.2 Dynamic Analysis

For the precise description of the dynamic behavior of the dual robotic system with integrated linear displacement, the recursive Newton–Euler method was used. The method allows the calculation of the moments and forces required to perform specific movements, considering the inertias of the joints, the centrifugal and Coriolis forces, as well as gravity. The analysis is carried out separately for each arm, while their interaction is considered through the external forces acting on the common manipulated object. For each link i , the angular/linear accelerations are given based on the following:

Angular Acceleration given via Eq. (10):

$$\dot{\omega}_i = R_{i-1}^i \cdot \omega_{i-1} + \zeta_i \cdot \ddot{q}_i + \omega_i \cdot (\zeta_i \cdot \dot{q}_i) \quad (10)$$

Linear Acceleration of the center of mass in Eq. (11):

$$\ddot{U}_{ci} = \ddot{u}_i + \dot{\omega}_{i-1} \times r_i + \omega_i \times (\omega_i \times r_i) \quad (11)$$

where R_{i-1}^i is the rotation matrix from frame $i-1$ to i , $z_i = [0 \ 0 \ 1]^T$ for revolute joints and $\zeta_i = [0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$ for prismatic joints, P_{i-1}^i is the vector from joint $i-1$ to i , r_i is the vector from joint i to the center of mass of link i .

Then, using Newton's second law for translation and Euler's law for rotation, we calculate force and torque from Eq. (12) and (13):

$$f_i = m_i \cdot \ddot{U}_{ci} \quad (12)$$

$$n_i = I_i \cdot \dot{\omega}_i + \omega_i \times (I_i \cdot \omega_i) \quad (13)$$

therefore, the force and torque transmitted to the previous link in Eq. (14) and (15):

$$F_{i-1} = R_{i-1}^{i-1}(f_i + F_i) \quad (14)$$

$$N_{i-1} = R_{i-1}^{i-1}(n_i + N_i + P_i \times f_i + r_i \times f_i) \quad (15)$$

When the recursive process is completed for all links, the full vector of joint torques τ is obtained [3] as a function of q , \dot{q} and \ddot{q} in Eq. (16):

$$\tau(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q}) = M(q) \cdot \ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q}) \cdot \dot{q} + g(q) \quad (16)$$

where $M(q)$ is the inertia matrix, $C(q, \dot{q})$ includes Coriolis and centrifugal effects and $g(q)$ is the gravity vector.

5 Simulation of the cooperative arms and the platform

The next step concerns the dynamic analysis through the simulation of a "pick and place" scenario with a 1 kg load, which was implemented in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. Initially, the behavior of each robotic arm is examined independently Fig. 4a, to calculate the required torque for lifting the load shown in Fig. 4b.

Fig. 4. Robotic Arm with Linear Displacement in Pick & Place Simulation

The total duration of the pick and place scenario is 30 seconds and includes the phases of lifting, transporting and placing the object. During the simulation, sensors (such as the Matlab transform and joint torque sensors) are used, which allow the recording of the required torque as a function of time. In this way, torque-time diagrams are obtained, which allow the comparison of the stress on the motors when only one robotic arm operates in relation to the case where the two arms cooperate.

6 Development and experimentation

To demonstrate the proposed approach, only one of the two robotic arms was constructed, weighing 3.5 kgs, where the theoretical analyses, design assumptions, and simulation results were confirmed. The robotic arm was designed using CAD software (Fusion 360) and implemented using 3D printing and PETG material and basic machining techniques as shown in Fig 5a and Fig 5b.

(a) (b)
Fig. 5. 3D Printed Robotic Arm

Its functionality was tested¹ through basic tests which were designed to simulate the operation scenario of one arm. Through the tests, it was possible to:

- Validate the kinematic behavior,
- Evaluate the mechanism's physical characteristics, such as accuracy, durability, and ease of assembly.
- Repeatability tests of each joint's accuracy were performed

The successful construction and operation of the arm attached to a linear joint on the rover confirms the validity of the simulation and design, providing the foundation for the future completion of the two-arm collaborative system.

¹ Video Demonstration: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SzkkpGk_IEI
 Payload Demonstration: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B8qeLWHeAQE>

7 Conclusions

This study presented the development of a collaborative dual-arm robotic system, where each arm featuring five rotational joints and a linear displacement mechanism. The complete system is attached to a rover. The introduction of the linear rail significantly enhanced the workspace and addressed reachability limitations commonly encountered in mobile manipulation scenarios. Through kinematic and dynamic analyses, the system's motion capabilities and torque requirements were thoroughly evaluated, while simulations demonstrated the benefits of collaborative manipulation in terms of reduced joint loads and increased operational efficiency. The construction and testing of one robotic arm validated the theoretical models. The successful integration of the proposed linear displacement mechanism enables the robotic platform to adapt more effectively to unstructured and confined environments. Future developments will focus on incorporating autonomous perception and decision-making modules, while integrating the system onto a larger scale mobile robotic platforms and rovers for real-world deployment in planetary exploration and related applications.

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